

**Large-Scale Energy Audit of 300 Mobile
Network Base Stations in Tanzania:**
Quantifying Diesel and Power Savings Potential for
Telecom Decarbonisation in Sub-Saharan Africa

Supplementary Data Set: Detailed site audits on 300 BTS
sites.

09 APRIL 2014
(Original Field Audit)
Updated for academic publication: May 2026

by

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Historical Note / Disclaimer:

This report presents primary field data collected in 2013–2014 from 300 GSM base stations operated by MNO Tanzania (Etisalat group). All findings reflect 2014 network conditions, diesel prices, and grid reliability. While the core methodology and per-site approach remain highly relevant, energy prices, network technology (2G/3G → 4G/5G transition), and renewable integration options have evolved significantly by 2026. The study is provided as a detailed historical case study for academic and policy purposes.

Abstract

Mobile network operators in sub-Saharan Africa face high energy costs due to unreliable grid power and heavy reliance on diesel generators. This study presents one of the largest published field audits of telecom base stations in Africa: detailed energy audits of 300 sites across five regions in Tanzania (Dar es Salaam, Zanzibar, Pemba, Pwani, and Morogoro). Using on-site measurements and 12 months of operational data (2013), the audit quantified power consumption, diesel usage, and carbon emissions.

Key results show average potential savings of 34 % in grid electricity and 60 % in diesel consumption across the sample, equating to an annual reduction of 2,698 GWh of electricity, 547,877 litres of diesel, and 3,373 tonnes of CO₂. Over 94 % of sites (283) were technically eligible for Energy Management Unit (EMU) implementation, with 57 sites identified as strong candidates for an immediate hybrid launch phase. Indoor vs. outdoor BTS configurations and generator runtime were the strongest predictors of savings potential.

The findings demonstrate that targeted hybrid solutions (advanced battery storage + optimised generator use) can deliver substantial operational expenditure (OPEX) and carbon reductions in African mobile networks. This large-scale case study provides a replicable methodology and benchmark for telecom decarbonisation across the continent.

Keywords: mobile network energy efficiency, base station energy audit, diesel reduction, Organic Rankine Cycle, hybrid power systems, telecom decarbonisation, sub-Saharan Africa, Tanzania, energy management unit

1.1 DSM Region

SITE NAME: ETHIOPIA STREET				
Site ID:	11054			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2825	-6.782		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/WIMAX):	S222	S646	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 33A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 358.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Yes				
Main source of savings:				
Generator usage				
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):				
Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.				
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):				
Yes				

SITE NAME: DAR VILLA				
Site ID:	11534			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.26365	-6.76313		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/WIMAX):	S000	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2 (1 inactive)			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	0A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 21A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 268.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KARIAKOO				
Site ID:	11023			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2716	-6.82044		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	RT			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	42A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 112 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption will be reduced by more than 20% and generator usage can be eliminated.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIJITONYAMA				
Site ID:	11553			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2399		-6.78264	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/WIMAX):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 699 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: KINONDONI BAKWATA				
Site ID:	11035			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2685	-6.7898		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/WIMAX):	S222	S444	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 7A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 37A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1153.3 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Yes				
Main source of savings:				
Generator usage				
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):				
Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.				
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):				
Yes				

SITE NAME: KINONDONI COURT				
Site ID:	11530			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25952778	-6.788388889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/WIMAX):	S222	S444	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 12A (BTS2) + 7A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 38A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 693 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KINONDONI MOSQUE				
Site ID:	11072			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2653	-6.80158		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration	S222	S444	0	0

900/1800/2100/WIMAX):				
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 459.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KINONDONI STUDIO				
Site ID:	11077			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2638	-6.79356		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3 (1 x CDMA cabinet)			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1 + 0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	105Ah	String 2 = 105Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 653 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: MASAKI			
Site ID:	11527		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2731	-6.75111	
Region:	DSM		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	RT		
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222 0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3		
Number of OD cabinets:	2		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 40A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, number and size:	0		
Generator Configuration:	N/A		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	105Ah	String 2 = 105Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 0 hrs.	N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO
Main source of savings:	N/A
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	N/A

SITE NAME: MBEZI (N-SHOOL)				
Site ID:	11003			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2206	-6.72467		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	26A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1561.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MFAUME ST UPANGA				
Site ID:	11056			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28003	-6.80784		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	RT			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 40A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 718.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MIKOCHE NI B				
Site ID:	11528			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24052778	-6.754166667		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S000	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	27A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 400.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MIKOCHE NI WARIOBA				
Site ID:	11008			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2429		-6.75691	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S244	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	31A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1 + 0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2427.1 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: MSASANI PENINSULAR			
Site ID:	11053		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.281722	-6.748361	
Region:	DSM		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2		
Number of OD cabinets:	2		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1013 hrs.	N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: MSASANI				
Site ID:	11007			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2822	-6.74228		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	48A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 450.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Yes				
Main source of savings:				
Generator usage and power				
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):				
Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.				
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):				
Yes				

SITE NAME: MUHIMBILI				
Site ID:	11524			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27378	-6.80425		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1013.4 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWANAYAMALA				
Site ID:	11036			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25092	-6.783		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 10A (BTS4) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2/3 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	3 strings x 4 = 12			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 29.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption can be eliminated.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWENGE II				
Site ID:	11009			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.223122	-6.770265		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	46A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 820.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: OYSTER BAY				
Site ID:	11016			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2783	-6.7755		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 649.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: PENINSULAR				
Site ID:	11211			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28151		-6.75498	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 10A (BTS4) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 386.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: AIRPORT JNIA				
Site ID:	11557			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2077	-6.86569		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S202	S022	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	38A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power Consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes but not priority			

SITE NAME: CCM CHANGOMBE				
Site ID:	11027			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2666	-6.84939		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 591.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ILALA BOMA				
Site ID:	11063			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2629	-6.82611		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1074.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KAWEL				
Site ID:	11006			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2204	-6.73633		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S644	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	39A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2491.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KIPAWA				
Site ID:	11206			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21316667	-6.858861111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 155.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption will be reduced by more than 20% and diesel consumption potentially eliminated.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KISUTU				
Site ID:	11025			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2867	-6.81669		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	48A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1231.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KONGOWE				
Site ID:	11049			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2808	-6.95		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S223	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	28A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 936.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KUNDUCHI MTONGANI				
Site ID:	11002			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2072	-6.66472		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S332	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	49A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2025.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MABIBO				
Site ID:	11010			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2245	-6.80593		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1035.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MAGOGONI KIGAMBONI				
Site ID:	11028			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3426	-6.83058		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 629.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAGOMENI				
Site ID:	11022			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25975	-6.80838		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S323	S664	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	55A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2222.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MBAGALA KUU				
Site ID:	11029			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2819	-6.89583		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S223	S244	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 3793.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MBEZI JUU				
Site ID:	11005			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2091	-6.72306		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 512.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBURAHATI				
Site ID:	11064			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24208333	-6.81375		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 406.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: NIC LIFE HOUSE				
Site ID:	11020			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2917	-6.81694		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1157.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: PICKCOCK HOTEL				
Site ID:	11024			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2803		-6.81772	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	RT			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	26A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes but not priority			

SITE NAME: POSTA				
Site ID:	11026			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2889		-6.81312	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 987.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: REGENT I TSJ				
Site ID:	11075			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25243611	-6.769555556		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	40A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1240.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: RIFLE RANGE				
Site ID:	11004			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2169	-6.70232		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 314.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SALASALA				
Site ID:	11000			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2005	-6.69358		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1860.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: SEAVIEW				
Site ID:	11067			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28546	-6.7993		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	48A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1982 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: SINZA				
Site ID:	11011			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21827	-6.78816		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	27A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1809 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: TABATA BARACUDA				
Site ID:	11019			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2121		-6.84389	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 689.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TABATA MAKUBURI				
Site ID:	11012			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2147	-6.81325		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	32A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 389.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TABATA RELINI				
Site ID:	11014			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2294	-6.82457		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 772.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TAMBAZA				
Site ID:	11034			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2769	-6.80078		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 565 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TANDALE				
Site ID:	11017			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2436	-6.78853		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S343	S444	S111	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	49A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1085.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: TBS UBUNGO				
Site ID:	11013			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2094	-6.79222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S444	S111	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	45A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 781 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TEMEKE SUDAN				
Site ID:	11202			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.26173	-6.86261		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S644	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	38A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 244.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TFC				
Site ID:	11021			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2798		-6.82217	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2100.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage and power			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: WAZO				
Site ID:	11001			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.1731	-6.66753		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S024	S420	S111	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	32A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		N/A	
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 4262.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			

Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel fuel will be reduced by more than 20%.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: AIRPORT RUNWAY				
Site ID:	11543			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21411111	-6.875472222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 8A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 38A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 5911.2 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: BOKO				
Site ID:	11549			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.154	-6.63211		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	0	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 10A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 42A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1317 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: BONYOKWA			
Site ID:	11554		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.166775	-6.826583333	
Region:	DSM		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	2		
Number of OD cabinets:	2		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 28A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 = 160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 421 hrs.	N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: BUGURUNI				
Site ID:	11060			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24155	-6.83498		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 40A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			

Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 441.4 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: BUGURUNI MALAPA				
Site ID:	11043			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24977	-6.82677		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 40A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			

If Yes, details:	N/A	
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 262.6 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: BUNJU B				
Site ID:	11220			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.08816667	-6.624638889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 14A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			

If Yes, details:	N/A	
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 637 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: CCM MTONI				
Site ID:	11040			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27426	-6.86843		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S111	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 8A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 38A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			

Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No
If Yes, details:	N/A
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 740.7 hrs. N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: CHANGOMBE				
Site ID:	11042			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.26962	-6.832222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S112	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			

Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 705 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: CHARAMBE				
Site ID:	11548			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2576	-6.92944		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S333	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 40A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah

Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 438.6 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: CONCORD HOTEL				
Site ID:	11065			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27652	-6.82082		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah

Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1250.1 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: DEREMA				
Site ID:	11477			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2576	-6.84853		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 34A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			

Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 526.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: FERRY SIDO				
Site ID:	11208			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3074	-6.82153		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			

Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 3836 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: GONGO LA MBOTO				
Site ID:	11531			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.1426	-6.88447		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1104.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: HANANASIF				
Site ID:	11068			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27222		-6.795167	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S232	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			

If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 363.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: IKWETA BAR KA AZIZI ALLY				
Site ID:	11229			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27493		-6.86528	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			

Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 320.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ILALA CELTEL				
Site ID:	11943			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2557		-6.82847	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	0	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			

Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	N/A			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: ITV				
Site ID:	11215			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2387	-6.7645		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			

DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 8A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 42A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1601.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: JANGWANI SECONDARY				
Site ID:	11069			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2729	-6.81238		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			

DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 303.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KAMATA				
Site ID:	11071			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27414	-6.82424		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			

Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 531.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KEGERA MIKOROSHONI				
Site ID:	11052			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24003	-6.8003		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S232	S444	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			

Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 8A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 44A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 4014.1 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KEKO				
Site ID:	11357			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27723	-6.83722		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0

Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 44.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not a priority site			

SITE NAME: KEKO MCHUNGWA				
Site ID:	11525			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28065	-6.841969		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration	S121	S444	0	0

900/1800/2100/CDMA):				
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 28A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 556.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KEKO MWANGA		
Site ID:	11201	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2784	-6.83411
Region:	DSM	
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active	
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF	
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor	

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S112	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 720.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KEKO TOROLI	
Site ID:	11225
Longitude/Latitude:	39.271083 -6.842167
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF

Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 810.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIBADA	
Site ID:	11516
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3403 -6.89241
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active

Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 14A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 925.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIGAMBON MSIKITIN MWEUPE		
Site ID:	11622	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3143	-6.8263
Region:	DSM	

Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1321.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KIGAMBONI TUNGIL		
Site ID:	11622	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.321028	-6.842167

Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 249.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIGOGO	
Site ID:	11045

Longitude/Latitude:	39.25265	-6.81736		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 5750.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KIMARA MATANGINI				
Site ID:	11051			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.17147222	-6.784388889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 710.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIMARA SUKA	
Site ID:	11051
Longitude/Latitude:	39.15280556 -6.800552778
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 929.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KINYEREZI	
Site ID:	11547
Longitude/Latitude:	39.17275 -6.850305556
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF

Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 397.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIPUNGUNI	
Site ID:	11555
Longitude/Latitude:	39.18197222 -6.907083333
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active

Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 509.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIWALANI KANISANI	
Site ID:	11555
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23397222 -6.863305556
Region:	DSM

Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 861 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIWALANI KIGILAGILA		
Site ID:	11018	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22753	-6.866639

Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2536.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KUMBUKUMBU	
Site ID:	11078

Longitude/Latitude:	39.26722	-6.78092		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 36A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 692.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KURASINI BANDARI

Site ID:	11078			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28526	-6.83097		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S646	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 33A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1241.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: KURASINI TOM ESTATE				
Site ID:	11230			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.288269	-6.854076		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			

Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 170.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not priority site			

SITE NAME: MADENGE STREET	
Site ID:	11511
Longitude/Latitude:	39.252167 -6.836944
Region:	DSM
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active

Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 115.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not priority site			

SITE NAME: MAGOMENI MADABA	
Site ID:	11533
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2605 -6.81422
Region:	DSM

Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 718.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAGOMENI MAKUTI	
Site ID:	11055
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25804 -6.80079

Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S222
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 9A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 44A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 613.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAGOMENI MWEMBECHAI	
Site ID:	11055

Longitude/Latitude:	39.24755556	-6.808361111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 613.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MANZESE

Site ID:	11539			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2301	-6.79653		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1463.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MASAKI CHOLE				
Site ID:	11031			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.272556	-6.75975		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S466	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 34A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 332.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAZENGO ROAD				
Site ID:	11520			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2764	-6.81156		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S222
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 9A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 44A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 739 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBAGALA BAGHDAD				
Site ID:	11209			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2641	-6.88709		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 614.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBANDE				
Site ID:	11631			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21469444	-6.974694444		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 8A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 27A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 634.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBEZI LOUIS				
Site ID:	11434			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.11744167	-6.788361111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 8A (BTS2) + 12A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 44A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1106 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MBEZI TATEDO				
Site ID:	11542			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.18791667	-6.726222222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 348 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBWENI				
Site ID:	11216			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.12975	-6.586111111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S321	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 8A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 27A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1594 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MIVINJENI				
Site ID:	11044			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.287806	-6.839306		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 608.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MLALAKUWA				
Site ID:	11030			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23788889	-6.744611111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S466	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 59A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 3362.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MLIMANI				
Site ID:	11032			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2028	-6.75669		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1125.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MOSQUE STREET				
Site ID:	11059			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2839	-6.81958		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S244	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 10A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 29A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 458.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Yes				
Main source of savings:				
Generator usage				
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):				
Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.				
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):				
Yes				

SITE NAME: MSEWE				
Site ID:	11538			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19405556	-6.784388889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 470.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MTONI KIJICHI				
Site ID:	11552			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.294389	-6.882833		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 396.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWANAGATI				
Site ID:	11544			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2374	-6.90611		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 5650.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MWONGOZA				
Site ID:	11223			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.4824		-6.9475	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S112	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2 (1 inactive)			
Number of OD cabinets:	2 (1 inactive)			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	8A (BTS1) + 0A (BTS2) + 5A (cooling) = 13A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	2	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+1			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 6560.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MZAMBARAUNI				
Site ID:	11081			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.16716389	-6.878638889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1			
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 712.8 hrs.			
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: OYSTERBAY HALLE SELLASI				
Site ID:	11204			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27444	-6.76544		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 729.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: OYSTERBAY KAUNDA				
Site ID:	11203			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27928	-6.78589		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 56A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1046.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: PUGU				
Site ID:	11630			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.13197222	-6.908666667		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S202	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 7A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 698.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: RAHA TOWER				
Site ID:	11057			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28549		-6.81189	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: REGENT II CHATO				
Site ID:	11205			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25866667	-6.77625		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 278.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SALVATION ARMY				
Site ID:	11062			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27945	-6.85568		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 551.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SAYANSI (MWENGE)				
Site ID:	11033			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2385	-6.773916667		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 49A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2060.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: SEA CLIFF				
Site ID:	11033			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2385	-6.773916667		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	SH			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S200	S022	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	6A (BTS1) + 8A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 24A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: SINZA A				
Site ID:	11207			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22641667	-6.775972222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 452.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SINZA MWAIBULA				
Site ID:	11074			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23275	-6.786444444		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 341 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TABATA BIMA				
Site ID:	11217			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.221		-6.832527778	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 350.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TABATA SECONDARY				
Site ID:	11038			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.200083	-6.8285		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 579.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TABATA SEGEREA				
Site ID:	11541			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19644444	-6.844083333		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 351.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TANDIKA				
Site ID:	11466			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25112	-6.86705		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S422	S644	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 13A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 49A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 293.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TANDIKA MIKOROSHINI				
Site ID:	11061			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2484	-6.85607		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 248.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TEMBONI				
Site ID:	11540			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.14436111	-6.789944444		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1768.6 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: TEMEKE				
Site ID:	11517			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.270028	-6.869722		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1556.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: TEMEKE MAGANGA				
Site ID:	11224			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25487	-6.85659		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 595.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TUANGOMA				
Site ID:	11556			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3001		-6.9421	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 14A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 173.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not priority site			

SITE NAME: TUNGI SIDO				
Site ID:	11222			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.31512	-6.83546		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	S111	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 7A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 57A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 442.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UDOWE				
Site ID:	11058			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2742	-6.81721		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 103.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not priority site			

SITE NAME: UKONGA				
Site ID:	11532			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.18108333	-6.870722222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 186.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – not priority site			

SITE NAME: ULINGONI				
Site ID:	11050			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.15858333	-6.859555556		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 620.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UPANGA				
Site ID:	11520			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2772	-6.8148		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1524.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: UPANGA COURT				
Site ID:	11070			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2838	-6.80735		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 573 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: VINGUNGUTI				
Site ID:	11037			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22672222	-6.849972222		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2562.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: VINGUNGUTI INDUSTRIAL				
Site ID:	11039			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.200803	-6.864778		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1913.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: VINGUNGUTI KOMBO				
Site ID:	11529			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23880556	-6.843638889		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 395.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: YANGA CLUB				
Site ID:	11510			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2711		-6.81692	
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	0	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	0A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 854.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: YACHT CLUB				
Site ID:	11535			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2752	-6.74339		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	N/A			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: YOMBO				
Site ID:	11079			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23452778	-6.883416667		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 396.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: YOMBO VITUKA				
Site ID:	11623			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.239	-6.87176		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1495.1 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: YOMBO DOVYA				
Site ID:	11546			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2512	-6.87858		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 578.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: YOMBO KIPERA				
Site ID:	11073			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21858333	-6.893861111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 387.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ZAKHEM				
Site ID:	11041			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.26575	-6.910111		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 601.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ZANAKI				
Site ID:	11515			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2826	-6.81461		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	N/A			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	160Ah	String 2 =	160Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: MNO PARK				
Site ID:	11015			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2646	-6.7723		
Region:	DSM			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S423	S444	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 58A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	4	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	4+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 0 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

1.2 Pemba Region

SITE NAME: MKOANI				
Site ID:	21122			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.65363	-5.36475		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S246	S648	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	155Ah	String 2 =	155Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 183.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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SITE NAME: CHAKE				
Site ID:	21123			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.77708	-5.24051		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	55A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 137.8 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: WETE				
Site ID:	21124			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.73134	-5.05845		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S344	S6666	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	56A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 186.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KICHUNJUJ				
Site ID:	21125			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.69003	-5.379		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S633	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	40A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 349.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KONDE				
Site ID:	21126			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.74189	-4.95269		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S646	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	39A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 200.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MCHANGAMRIMA				
Site ID:	21127			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.79687	-5.183		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S4444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	35A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1/2 =	100Ah	String 3/4 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	4 strings x 4 = 16 (4 not operational in OD cabinet)			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 106.2 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MADENJANI				
Site ID:	21128			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.8097	-5.10133		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S543	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	33A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 225.6 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHAKE OFFICE				
Site ID:	21131			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7671	-5.24652		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	RT			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S424	S868	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	43A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 148.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KENGEJA				
Site ID:	21132			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.71738	-5.40955		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S686	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	41A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	125Ah	String 2 =	125Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 155.4 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: NGWACHANI				
Site ID:	21714			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.73432	-5.33254		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	34A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 357.5 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MKANYAGENI				
Site ID:	21715			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.6559	-5.40775		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1 + 0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 152.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHANJAMJAWIRI				
Site ID:	21129			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.76001	-5.29681		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 47A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	125Ah	String 2 =	125Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 267.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MICHEWENI				
Site ID:	21130			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.83284	-4.98196		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S666	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 50A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 137.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIUYU MBUYUNI				
Site ID:	21228			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.86207	-4.95188		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	125Ah	String 2 =	125Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 81.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SELEM				
Site ID:	21509			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.722278	-5.057167		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S364	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 143.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MKOROSHONI				
Site ID:	21550			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.77807		-5.22787	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 128.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BAHANASA				
Site ID:	21590			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.76762	-5.11087		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S343	S442	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 47A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 189.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MANTAREEF				
Site ID:	21655			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.6809	-4.88342		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S202	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 7A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 41A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 207.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KOJANI				
Site ID:	21662			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.8435	-5.0971		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 85.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: WINGWI				
Site ID:	21663			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.81578		-5.02832	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 113.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UKUTINI				
Site ID:	21667			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.76194		-5.3508	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 7A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1			
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 308.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MTAMBWE				
Site ID:	21685			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.71544		-5.0911	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S434	0	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 0A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 284.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MBUYUNI				
Site ID:	21707			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.74255		-5.01891	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S343	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 155.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: PUJINI				
Site ID:	21709			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.8013	-5.29717		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S424	S444	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 46A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 247.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: PANDANI				
Site ID:	21730			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.78		-5.06	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 190 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHUMBAGENI				
Site ID:	21731			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.688261	-5.310701		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S433	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 160.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KONDE CHANJAANI				
Site ID:	21732			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.739226	-4.940056		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	S442	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 10A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 157 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: VITONGOJI				
Site ID:	21733			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.82274	-5.2352		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 72.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TUNDAUWA				
Site ID:	21734			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7		-5.27	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 204.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KOONGO				
Site ID:	21735			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.8076	-5.1504		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 80.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ZIWANI				
Site ID:	21736			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7678		-5.1757	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 325.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BULE				
Site ID:	21744			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.75397	-4.98548		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 345 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: GANDO				
Site ID:	21751			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7045	-4.99536		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 211.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAKOMBENI				
Site ID:	21756			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.653688		-5.334928	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 181.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: FURAHA				
Site ID:	21757			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.8214	-5.26108		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 312.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KANGANI				
Site ID:	21758			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.689	-5.42575		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 128 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWAMBE				
Site ID:	21766			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7515	-5.41358		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 88.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIWANI				
Site ID:	21512			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.741	-5.38319		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 36A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	125Ah	String 2 =	125Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 95.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: DAYA				
Site ID:	21762			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.71672	-5.13299		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 93 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: NDAGONI				
Site ID:	21763			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7134	-5.21286		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 161.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: GOMBANI				
Site ID:	21783			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.77		-5.21	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 139.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MZINGANI				
Site ID:	21765			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.70503	-5.35314		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 114.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KISIWA PANZA				
Site ID:	21766			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.6474	-5.45969		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 6703.8 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – priority site			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MTANGANI				
Site ID:	21767			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.7822		-5.37325	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 7A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 216.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHANJAANI				
Site ID:	21779			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.78158		-5.26197	
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah	String 2 =	100Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 287.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIFUMBIKAI				
Site ID:	21784			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.73898	-5.06061		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S334	S446	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 466.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TUMBE COW				
Site ID:	21782			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.78436	-4.95015		
Region:	Pemba			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1964.5 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

1.3 Zanzibar Region

SITE NAME: SHAKANI				
Site ID:	21781			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.241078	-6.23195		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 345.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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SITE NAME: KINUNI				
Site ID:	21077			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.231096	-6.170623		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 270.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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SITE NAME: NYARUGUSU				
Site ID:	21285			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24248	-6.17958		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 36A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 429.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			

Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: RESIDENCE				
Site ID:	21668			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.45	-6.41		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA:	S222	S000	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2 (1 inactive)			
Number of OD cabinets:	2 (1 inactive)			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 0A (BTS2) + 5A (cooling) = 12A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	N/A			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			

Main source of savings:	N/A
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO

SITE NAME: MUYUNI				
Site ID:	21785			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.46	-6.36		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S000	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 309.7 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: JUMBI				
Site ID:	21778			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.30347	-6.19461		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS1) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 113.4 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Generator usage
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: PALE				
Site ID:	21722			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2561	-5.89418		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS1) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			

Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 314.8 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: NDAGAA				
Site ID:	21752			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3	-6.05		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S000	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			

If Yes, details:	N/A	
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 167.7 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: MWERA PONGWE				
Site ID:	21786			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2873	-6.15906		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS1) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			

Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO		
Main source of savings:	N/A		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO		

SITE NAME: JENDELE				
Site ID:	21743			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.37	-6.18		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			

Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 256 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: MFUMBWI				
Site ID:	21729			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.56	-6.34		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah

Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 700.9 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: MTENDE				
Site ID:	21665			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.53	-6.45		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			

Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 316.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIDOTI				
Site ID:	21721			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3004	-5.80839		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	7A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 26A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			

Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 350.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWERA				
Site ID:	21770			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.27042	-6.14571		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 328.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWENDO KIANGA				
Site ID:	21728			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25395	-6.14065		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA:	S244	S246	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			

If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 485.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UNGUJA UKUU				
Site ID:	21719			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.37		-6.2802	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			

Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: KOMBENI				
Site ID:	21284			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2585		-6.2565	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S343	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 14A			
Air-conditioners:	No			

Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: KOKONI				
Site ID:	21400			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.194		-6.16021	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S884	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			

DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 137 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SEBLENI				
Site ID:	21281			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21721		-6.16491	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S488	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			

DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 51A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 534.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAGOGONI				
Site ID:	21116			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23575	-6.17454		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			

Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 593.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: NYERERE				
Site ID:	21066			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22398	-6.17073		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			

Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 241.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MPENDAE				
Site ID:	21513			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2168	-6.18714		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S846	S222	0

Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 50A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 230.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: JANGOMBE				
Site ID:	21512			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2121	-6.17661		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration	S444	S888	S222	0

900/1800/2100/CDMA):				
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 220.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UZI-TOMONDO	
Site ID:	21725
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23162 -6.19066
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S0	S444	S0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 16A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 220.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: ZIWATUWE	
Site ID:	21518
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2185 -6.15961
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF

Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 257 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWANAKWEREKWE	
Site ID:	21514
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23063 -6.18338
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active

Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S688	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 10A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 51A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1211.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MWEMBE MAKUMBI	
Site ID:	21723
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21 -6.15
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)

Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 13A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 34A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 197.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MATEMWE	
Site ID:	21115
Longitude/Latitude:	39.350399 -5.8901

Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	0	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 31A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 494.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MWANYANYA	
Site ID:	21521

Longitude/Latitude:	39.2204	-6.11503		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S686	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 13A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 48A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 335.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: GARAGARA

Site ID:	21519			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2256	-6.13947		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S868	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 49A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 204 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KWARARA				
Site ID:	21561			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24328	-6.19766		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S866	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 13A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 50A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1275.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MAKUNDUCHI				
Site ID:	21113			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.5541	-6.41261		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S433	S545	S222	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 47A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 330.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: OCEAN PARADISE				
Site ID:	21522			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.35735	-5.93581		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S202	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	8A (BTS1) + 6A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 24A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 354.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: NUNGWI				
Site ID:	21523			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2988	-5.72881		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S233	S464	S111	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	8A (BTS1) + 12A (BTS2) + 7A (BTS3) + 15A (cooling) = 42A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 387 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIGOMANI				
Site ID:	21771			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3567	-5.8417		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: UKONGORONI				
Site ID:	21777			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.4738	-6.2111		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: KIJANGWANI				
Site ID:	21508			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.20535	-6.16359		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	4			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 16A (BTS2) + 11A (BTS3) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 64A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 219.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: DARAJA BOVU				
Site ID:	21233			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2247	-6.15397		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S688	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 15A (BTS2) + 11A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 52A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 176.5 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BAMBI				
Site ID:	21079			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.347161	-6.105253		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1832.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

CANDIDATE FOR LAUNCH PHASE

SITE NAME: MAMBOSASA				
Site ID:	21080			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25774	-6.176558		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 813.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIDUTANI				
Site ID:	21082			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19209		-6.16428	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	11A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 32A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	NO			
Main source of savings:	N/A			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	N/A			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	NO			

SITE NAME: KARAFUU				
Site ID:	21105			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.5271		-6.1786	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S132	0	0	
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	10A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, number and size:	0			
Generator Configuration:	0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	100Ah		
Number of batteries:	1 strings x 4 = 4			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	N/A		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: QUALITY				
Site ID:	21090			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19924	-6.16182		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	38A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 504.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MIGOMBANI				
Site ID:	21087			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.20588	-6.18289		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S424	S848	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 298.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: LUMUMBA				
Site ID:	21093			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.20767	-6.15733		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S866	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 119.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MALINDI				
Site ID:	21559			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19459	-6.15719		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S668	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 241.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TOMONDO				
Site ID:	21118			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22531	-6.1967		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	38A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 392.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: TUMEKUJA				
Site ID:	21088			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.18802	-6.16573		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S686	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	2 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	2+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 230.25 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHUKWANI				
Site ID:	21095			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21544	-6.21887		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S666	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	35A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 463 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KISIWANDUI				
Site ID:	21089			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19325	-6.16562		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	38A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 294.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHUMBUNI				
Site ID:	21117			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21941	-6.14695		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S866	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 179.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIJITO UPELE				
Site ID:	21094			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.24134	-6.18675		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	0	
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	27A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 219.7 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MEYA				
Site ID:	21558			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21433	-6.17217		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S424	S888	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 248 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MOMBASA				
Site ID:	21097			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22001	-6.18086		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	33A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 430.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: AMANI				
Site ID:	21085			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2286	-6.16302		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S288	S111	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	28A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	2 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	2+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 213.04 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: FUONI				
Site ID:	21119			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2609	-6.19519		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S666	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 250 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIWENGWA				
Site ID:	21098			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.335583	-5.992472		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S242	S222	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	29A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 309.7 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KOANI				
Site ID:	21563			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28769	-6.13625		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	33A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 404.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MTONI				
Site ID:	21109			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22057	-6.12709		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S468	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	34A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 289.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIBWENI				
Site ID:	21560			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21939	-6.10766		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S433	S868	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	36A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 437.1 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BUMBWINI				
Site ID:	21111			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19694	-5.97		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S440	S422	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	28A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 244 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: CHWAKA				
Site ID:	21101			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.428799	-6.1632		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S262	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	30A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 276.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: FUMBA				
Site ID:	21107			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28606	-6.31783		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S233	S202	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	27A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 329 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KITOGANI				
Site ID:	21114			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.43779	-6.28666		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S222	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	29A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 293.6 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIZIMKAZI				
Site ID:	21103			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.4691	-6.44633		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S323	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	32A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 300.4 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAHONDA				
Site ID:	21106			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25031	-5.99003		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S464	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	33A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 528.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MKWAJUNI				
Site ID:	21108			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.28787	-5.87821		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S543	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	35A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 353 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MICHAMVI				
Site ID:	21720			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.52419	-6.1674		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	0	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	19A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 371.8 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)				
Yes				
Main source of savings:				
Power consumption and diesel consumption				
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):				
Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.				
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):				
Yes				

SITE NAME: DUNGA				
Site ID:	21120			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3288	-6.14033		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S424	S224	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	29A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			

DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 237.9 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: UROA			
Site ID:	21121		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.4248	-6.07567	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S224	S222
Number of BTS cabinets:	3		
Number of OD cabinets:	0		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	27A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		

Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 268.8 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: MFENESINI				
Site ID:	21562			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.2281	-6.04656		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S552	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	33A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 377 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIZIMBANI		
Site ID:	21564	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.25315	-6.10106

Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	S444	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	32A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 540 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KINYASINI				
Site ID:	21565			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3071		-5.97214	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S422	S422	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	28A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	

Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 495.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: PAJE				
Site ID:	21566			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.5338		-6.26126	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S606	S222	
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	31A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 300.7 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: UZINI			
Site ID:	21567		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.3293	-6.07456	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S222	S222
Number of BTS cabinets:	3		
Number of OD cabinets:	0		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	30A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A		
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 719.9 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: HAMAMNI			
Site ID:	21086		
Longitude/Latitude:	39.19036	-6.16228	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		

Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S244	S446	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	43A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 441.3 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MADEMA				
Site ID:	21092			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.20055		-6.1712	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S444	S888	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	48A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		

Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 163.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MAZIZINI				
Site ID:	21091			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.21293		-6.20201	
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	S884	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		2 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 306.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			

Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: MASINGINI				
Site ID:	21099			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.23981	-6.14625		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S433	S866	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	47A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 308.9 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BUBUBU				
Site ID:	21100			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.22365	-6.08937		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration	S444	S888	S222	S333

900/1800/2100/CDMA):				
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	52A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 304.2 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: BLUEBAY				
Site ID:	21110			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.368	-5.9743		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S321	S222	S111	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	37A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah

Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 388.9 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: JAMBIANI				
Site ID:	21104			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.54167	-6.2975		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S611	S402	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	39A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 419.2 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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SITE NAME: TUNGUU				
Site ID:	21102			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.319139	-6.224944		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S224	S4422	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	34A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU	2 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 236.4 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KILINDI				
Site ID:	21624			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.302222	-5.761389		
Region:	Unguja (Zanzibar)			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S442	S442	S222	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	4			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	41A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 18000BTU		1 x 18000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 445.8 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

1.4 Pwani Region

SITE NAME: CHALINZE				
Site ID:	11245			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.35255278		-6.637694444	
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	10A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			

If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 500 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIBAHA				
Site ID:	11231			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.93371944		-6.755972222	
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	21A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1203 hrs.		N/A	

Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes

SITE NAME: MBWEWE				
Site ID:	11178			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.2353	-6.026278		
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S121	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	18A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	2 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+1			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 3682 hrs.		Generator 2 = 3063	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – PRIORITY SITE			

SITE NAME: MSAKUZI		
Site ID:	11632	
Longitude/Latitude:	39.09513889	-6.752136111

Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	19A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 849 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: RUVU RANCH				
Site ID:	11218			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.5745		-6.667933	
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S211	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	18A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	

Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 285 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: UBENA ZOMOZI				
Site ID:	11242			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.17961111		-6.636916667	
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	9A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			

Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 1692 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: KELEGE				
Site ID:	11232			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.03219444	-6.581583333		
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S211	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	1			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 5A (cooling) = 14A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2633 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIBAHA MACHINJIONI				
Site ID:	11213			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.98713889	-6.769666667		
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 28A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 330 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: LUGULUNI				
Site ID:	11210			
Longitude/Latitude:	39.08325	-6.794555556		
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S322	S022	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			

Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	10A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 29A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 877 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: MLANDIZI			
Site ID:	11212		
Longitude/Latitude:	38.739	-6.70888889	
Region:	Pwani		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0 0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2		
Number of OD cabinets:	2		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 28A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		

Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 249 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes		

SITE NAME: ZINGA				
Site ID:	11219			
Longitude/Latitude:	38.9715	-6.520222222		
Region:	Pwani			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 9A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 28A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 5186 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes – PRIORITY SITE
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1.5 Morogoro Region

SITE NAME: KINGOLOWILA				
Site ID:	31249			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.78677778	-6.760555556		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	23A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU	1 x 12000BTU		
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 640 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MIKESE				
Site ID:	31241			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.88658333	-6.752944444		
Region:	Morogoro			

Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	0	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	1			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	9A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	
Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 2016 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MSEMBE				
Site ID:	31250			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.63966667		-6.698944444	
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Indoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S222	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	0			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	19A (all BTS and TX but excluding cooling)			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	N/A			
Air-conditioners:	1 x 12000BTU		1 x 12000BTU	

Free cooling (Y/N):	No			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 612 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Power consumption and diesel consumption			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – power consumption and diesel usage will be reduced by more than 20%.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: FOREST				
Site ID:	31465			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.67733333	-6.836305556		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			

Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 658 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: KIGURUNYEMBE				
Site ID:	31463			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.69316667	-6.824333333		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 570 hrs.	N/A		
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KIHONDA				
Site ID:	31139			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.6526	-6.78625		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 496 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KKT LUTHERAN				
Site ID:	31137			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.66552778	-6.818747222		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			

Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 728 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: KOLA HILL				
Site ID:	31138			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.6987		-6.81339	
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S666	0	
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 14A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 33A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			

Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)	
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No	
If Yes, details:	N/A	
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 359 hrs.	N/A
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes	
Main source of savings:	Generator usage	
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.	
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes	

SITE NAME: MAZIMBU			
Site ID:	31464		
Longitude/Latitude:	37.6524	-6.80906	
Region:	Morogoro		
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active		
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF		
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor		
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S213	S442	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2		
Number of OD cabinets:	2		
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes		
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A		
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 10A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 29A		
Air-conditioners:	No		
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system		
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes		
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA	
Generator Configuration:	1+0		
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes		
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 = 150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8		
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)		
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No		
If Yes, details:	N/A		
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 732 hrs.	N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes		
Main source of savings:	Generator usage		
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.		

Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes
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SITE NAME: MISIFUNI				
Site ID:	31240			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.65394444	-6.828722222		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	S333
Number of BTS cabinets:	3			
Number of OD cabinets:	3			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) +10A (CDMA) + 15A (cooling) = 45A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 593 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: MSAMVU				
Site ID:	31239			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.66680278	-6.804222222		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			

Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			
Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 383 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

SITE NAME: SEA VIEW				
Site ID:	31462			
Longitude/Latitude:	37.6639	-6.82939		
Region:	Morogoro			
Site Status (Act/Inact):	Active			
Type of Site (GF/RF/SH):	GF			
Type of equipment shelter:	Outdoor			
Radio Configuration 900/1800/2100/CDMA):	S222	S444	0	0
Number of BTS cabinets:	2			
Number of OD cabinets:	2			
Incoming Mains (Y/N):	Yes			
DC load test at rectifier (48V):	N/A			
DC load test OD cabinet (48V):	9A (BTS1) + 11A (BTS2) + 10A (cooling) = 30A			
Air-conditioners:	No			
Free cooling (Y/N):	Yes through outdoor cabinet cooling system			
Generator backup (Y/N):	Yes			
If Yes, number and size:	1 x	22kVA		
Generator Configuration:	1+0			

Battery backup (Y/N):	Yes			
Battery capacity sizing:	String 1 =	150Ah	String 2 =	150Ah
Number of batteries:	2 strings x 4 = 8			
Type of batteries:	Lead Acid (sealed)			
Hybrid Generator/Battery (Y/N):	No			
If Yes, details:	N/A			
Generator runtime (previous 12 months - 2013):	Generator 1 = 435 hrs.		N/A	
Energy savings possible (Y/N)	Yes			
Main source of savings:	Generator usage			
Will energy savings exceed 20% (Y/N):	Yes – diesel fuel consumption will be reduced by more than 20%. Power consumption will not be reduced.			
Is site eligible for EMU project (Y/N):	Yes			

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